

Research Paper

Transformational leadership a paradigm to initiative-oriented behaviour among the Managers in health care set up- literature review.

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Abstract: Due to extensive structural and functional reforms, presently we see lot of challenges, conflict and chaos. This brings to the need of appropriate leadership style, to manage the organisation and reach its goal.

Purpose of the present article is to analyse the literature based various leadership style and to discuss the various criteria needed for a leader as a transformational personality to manage the reforms in an organisation.

Methodology: the secondary sources like published literatures from scholarly journals acquired through Google scholar, pub med with the aid of key words and reference list are analysed and discussed in the frame work of the objectives. Systematic literature review-based analysis is used in the present study. 30 articles based on transformational leadership style was reviewed, among which 10 articles were chosen for the present article based on the criteria to understand the type, impact, influence of attributes and the strategies.

Findings: The review shows that there is a need to understand in-depth variables in order to understand specific dimension of the transformational leadership quality which will motivate the employees to work in the organisation without fatigue, stress or burnout. This brings the importance of conducting research with clear and strong research design, which can easily investigate the dimension of specifically to test more complicated relationship.

Originality of the present paper: we find several research based on the leadership style in an organisation. Transformation leadership is the need of the day because we witness lot of reforms in the organisation due to the changing needs of the customers and stakeholders. Hence an attempt is made to review the literature based on various issues like leadership style, impact on the employees, influence of various attributes and strategies to improve the leadership style to increase the quality of work in any organisation.

Further research: Reviewing the literatures and after analysing the author observes that although transformational leadership is understood in-depth, based on its impact on the work force of the organisation, there are few research gaps. Hence the author highlights the need for further research which should focus on identifying factors like psychological aspects of the stake holders in order to fit into the frame of the changing needs of the employees and the stake holder in any organisation.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, Initiative - oriented behaviour, Healthcare

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I. INTRODUCTION

Change in any sector is inevitable and is universal. Presently, we find that the organisations are undergoing extensive structural reforms. This brings into scene lot of challenges, conflict, and chaos, which is met by the initiatives of the management. To achieve positive structural reforms in any organisation, it requires support from the management and the commitment of the employees. This shows the urgency in an appropriate leader, who will move the organisation forward successfully amidst of all the challenges.

Transformational Leadership is a concept initiated by a political scientist James MacGragor Burns, which follows a motivational management approach. In this type of approach, the followers will take the leader as their role model, where the personality of the leader influences the team members. Transformation leadership focuses on long term strategy.

The core values for Transformational leadership is honesty and integrity which influences on the authenticity and transparency. The leader focuses his work on doing the right thing in the right way in the best interest of the organisation and the stake holders. One of the major advantage of this type of leadership in an organisation is that they have the potential to reverse the loss of productivity in the organisation. The very important factor of the transformational leadership is that they align the interest of the organisation with that of the employees. So when the reform occurs in the organisation, the leader is able to identify the areas that require for change and will create a corresponding vision. Hence the advantage is that the employees will experience autonomy over the roles and responsibilities. By employing the transformational leadership style, the leaders will work with honesty and integrity by being honest, and transparent, focusing on values and ethics. This will motivate the employees work on reducing attrition in the organisation. Change is suggestable in any organisation, hence adapting a transformational leadership style in a manager will help in recognising gaps in the right time enabling the organisation to adjust and constantly working to reach the vision. This also explains the positive impact of transformational leadership for the organisation.

However, the present author felt the need to understand the limitations of this leadership style also. Sometimes, transformational leaders, in the process of concentrating on the future goals, may overlook minor issues and processes. Since they concentrate on being a role model to other employees, they don't hesitate to take risk which may sometimes can become detrimental to the others in the organisation because of the work pressure, fatigue, and deadlines. There is also need for frequent training to the employees, which may increase the expenses of the organisation. There is also need for effective communication amidst the team, which includes the process of continuous feedback, meetings etc. which may lead to burnout. Adapting to frequent changes may sometime cause risk to the organization. This brings the need of creating faith by the leader to the employees, without which there will be increase in the industrial conflicts.

Bearing in mind these limitations, and the importance of the transformational leadership author felt the need to analyse the impact of transformational leadership, its criteria, associated factors, and the importance of transformational in the organisation. Analysis of these factors are conducted through reviewing published article in scientific journals.

OBJECTIVES OF THE REVIEW PAPER

1. To find various factors related to transformational leadership in the organisation
2. To review literature based on impact of the transformational leadership
3. To find the ideal characteristics on the transformational leader
4. To identify the research gap in the study area
5. Identifying various research agenda related to the study area
6. To choose a research agenda for further research based on priority

II. METHODOLOGY OF DATA COLLECTION

Systematic review of the various research conducted in the area of transformational leadership in the health care organisation will be conducted and the results of these review will be analysed based on the objectives.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE BASED ANALYSIS

SL.NO	AREA	FOCUS	REFERENCES
1.	Impact on followers	The study investigates the influence of the charismatic leadership on the followers, focusing on initiative-oriented behaviour in hospitals.	Boerner, Sabine & Dütshcke, Elisabeth. (2008). The impact of charismatic leadership on followers' initiative-oriented behavior: A study in German hospitals. Health care management review. 33. 332-40. 10.1097/01.HCM.0000318771.82642.8f.
2.	Facilitators of goal pursuit of employees	Linkage between transformational leadership and followers job attitudes focusing on the goal setting process.	Steinmann, B., Klug, H., & Maier, G. W. (2018). The Path Is the Goal: How Transformational Leaders Enhance Followers' Job Attitudes and Proactive Behavior. Frontiers in psychology, 9, 2338. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02338
3.	Impact of transformational leadership on work performance	Impact on reducing burnout and social loafing.	Khan, Hira & Rehmat, Maryam & Hassan Butt, Tahira & Farooqi, Saira & Asim, Javaria. (2020). Impact of transformational leadership on work performance, burnout and social loafing: a mediation model. Future Business Journal. 6. 10.1186/s43093-020-00043-8.
4.	Impact of transformational leadership on employee psychological well-being	Psychological well-being of the employees	Kara Arnold, (2017). Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, American Psychological Association, Vol. 22, No. 3, 381–393. DOI:10.1037/ocp0000062
5.	Influence of	Influence of the	Peng, S., Liao, Y., & Sun, R. (2020). The Influence of

	transformational leadership in Public and non-profit organisation	transformational leadership on the organisational commitment.	Transformational Leadership on Employees' Affective Organizational Commitment in Public and Nonprofit Organizations: A Moderated Mediation Model. Public Personnel Management, 49(1), 29–56. https://doi.org/10.1177/0091026019835233
6.	Transformational leadership in 21 st century	Expectations of transformational leadership quality in future.	Allan D. M. Bukusi. (2020). What Transformative Leaders do: Emerging Perspectives in the 21st Century, International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology, Vol.12 (4), pp. 85-93, October-December 2020. DOI: 10.5897/IJSA2020.0871
7.	Implementation of management reforms	Information use on the goal clarity and organisational culture.	Donald P. Moynihan, Sanjay K. Pandey, Bradley E. Wright (2012). Setting the Table: How Transformational Leadership Fosters Performance Information Use, Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory, Volume 22, Issue 1, January 2012, Pages 143–164, https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mur024
8.	Utilisation of resources of the leaders for better impact.	Peer support increases the effectiveness of transformational leadership behaviour	Susanne Tafvelin, Karina Nielsen, Ulrica von Thiele Schwarz & Andreas Stenling (2019) Leading well is a matter of resources: Leader vigour and peer support augments the relationship between transformational leadership and burnout, Work & Stress, 33:2, 156-172, DOI: 10.1080/02678373.2018.1513961
9.	Leadership style in Health care settings	Transformational leadership increases safety climate in the organisation, associated with patient safety outcome and overall quality care	Sfantou, D.F., Laliotis, A., Patelarou, A., Sifaki-Pistolla, D., Matalliotakis, M., & Patelarou, E. (2017). Importance of Leadership Style towards Quality of Care Measures in Healthcare Settings: A Systematic Review. Healthcare, 5.
10.	Challenges and strategies of transformational leadership	Transformational leadership contributing to the quality care of the patients.	Ferreira VB, Amestoy SC, Silva GTRD, Trindade LL, Santos IARD, Varanda PAG. Transformational leadership in nursing practice: challenges and strategies. Rev Bras Enferm. 2020;73(6):e20190364. Portuguese, English. doi: 10.1590/0034-7167-2019-0364. Epub 2020 Aug 10. PMID: 32785519.

III. DISCUSSION

In the study conducted by Boerner Sabine & Dütschke, Elisabeth. (2008)¹ 543 respondents consisting of medical staff who included physicians and nurses, in six German hospitals were investigated and hypothesis was tested conducted with hierarchical regression which interpreted the main effects and interactions. It was found that Charismatic leadership significantly predicted followers' initiative-oriented behaviour and the study confirmed the moderating effect of job autonomy. The positive impact on the followers was initiative-oriented behaviour in the hospital. The limitation of the study was the moderating effect of followers' stress was not confirmed by the research. Although it showed that that training can improve leaders' abilities in charismatic leadership, it highlighted the need for professional and intensified training. It also showed the need for frequent enhancement in the degree of follower's job autonomy during the change processes in the hospital.

Subsequently, in another study conducted by Steinmann, B., Klug, H., & Maier, G. W. (2018) found positive relations between follower-rated transformational leadership and their assessment of both goal attributes. This study further showed the increase in ideological vision of the employees who lay importance on the meaning of task which grant followers responsibility and support. So these behaviours results in the higher levels of identification with commitment to the organisational goals which are set by the leaders. Hence the transformational leadership behaviour promotes confidence in the follower's capability, increases opportunity for them significantly affecting their work, providing instrumental and emotional support, thus leading employees to further perceive their goal. Hence the author of the present article, highlights the importance of transformational leadership, which impacts the goal striving of the employees, by enhancing their perceptions of the importance of attaining the organisational goal. However, this study also showed few limitations. The result was based on self-report data, which may have desirability bias dealing with personal cognition and affect.

In another study conducted by Hira Khan, Maryam Rehmat, Tahira Hassan Butt, Saira Farooqi & Javaria Asim³, a cross sectional survey was conducted where data was collected among 308 employees of telecommunication. The study result showed that employee's positive work outcome could be increased by improving intrinsic motivation. This also will reduce the burnout and stress.

A systematic computerised search reviewed by Kara Arnold⁴ studied the prediction of impact of transformational leadership on the employee wellbeing. Forty paper were found which met the criteria of research question, reporting empirical results which highlights that the relationship is not simple. It suggest that there are several mediating variables, which shows indirect effect of transformational leadership on the

employee well-being. However, the study points out few limitations, on stronger research designs which need to investigate the dimensions of transformational leadership separately, to test more complicated relationship.

Research conducted by Peng, S., Liao, Y., & Sun, R⁵ contributes the understanding of potential structural factors which influenced by the transformational leadership quality of the management of the organisation. The study identifies the negative influence of centralisation on the commitment of the employees, as it strips autonomy and have less freedom to make decisions. The study also suggest to rule out potential organisational differences, while studying the impact of transformational leadership.

In a review study conducted by Allan D. M. Bukusi⁶, examines various articles published 2010 onwards, to understand current perspectives and theory, to provide leaders with a one stop reference document on the subject matter. The author analysed and thus the result revealed that the prospective transformational leaders is expected to do four important aspects, i.e., renew institutional vision and performance, advocate ethical and social advancement, empower individuals to make meaningful contribution to corporate goals, and sacrificially commit to realise the interests of those they serve. Thus this research would help the policy makers institutional leaders and business managers with insights on transformative leadership ethos and its potency to secure the benefits to the general population.

Donald P. Moynihan, Sanjay K. Pandey, Bradley E. Wright⁷ shares few view points by their research on the leadership affects the implementation of management reforms. The results of the study strongly points out that relationship between transformational leadership and performance information use is mediated by goal clarity and the developmental culture of the organisation.

Another study was reviewed, conducted by Susanne Tafvelin, Karina Nielsen, Ulrica von Thiele Schwarz & Andreas⁸ Stenling shed light on the relationship between transformational leadership and follower burnout. They highlighted that there should be interventions which aims to improve leaders internal resources like social support and vigour during the reforms in the work.

Sfantou, D.F., Laliotis, A., Patelarou, A., Sifaki-Pistolla, D., Matalliotakis, M., & Patelarou, E.⁹ conducted review of various literature conducted on .They found that most of the literature supported that the transformational leadership style is strongly linked to improved process quality, high organisation culture and positive patient outcome. They discussed that transformational leadership could be understood as a major indicator for developing qualitative organisational culture, with effective performance in health care provision. So it provided a safety environment which provided job satisfaction, higher productivity, retention, patient safety and overall safety culture with positive health outcomes.

Challenges and strategies with the transformational leadership in nursing practice was studied¹⁰ with an objective to understand the challenges and strategies adopted by nurses in a hospital. The reviews analysed that there were certain limitations like resistance to leadership, and in subordination. They also found lack of encouragement from the Institution. However, it was seen that the result showed relevance of practice in transformational leadership in providing quality of care.

RESEARCH GAP: The above review of literature uncovers various issues pertaining to the relevance of practice in transformational leadership in any kind of organisation. However, it also mentions certain research gap like, the qualitative approach in understanding the impact of transformational leadership style in the organisations. Because, it is understood that the transformational leadership profile is more open to suggestions and attentive to the needs of the consumers. Also, there is a need to understanding the perception of all the professionals working in the health care team about the transformational leadership style to develop an appropriate strategy for the organisation.

Author contribution: the future study could analyse the leadership behaviour by self-report measure because leaders tend to behave differently across situation. The study also should include the testing for systematic attrition and also find the differences between respondents and non-respondents. By understanding the impact of centralized structure of the organisation in one of the reviews, the author suggests to design a work strategy where opportunities could be provided to the employees where they could communicate directly with the beneficiaries to understand the nature of feedback and to improve their work. To build up a model for providing strategies transformational leaders are expected to learn from the past to challenge the turbulence of the future. Hence the author in the future research should contribute various approaches to meet the expectations of the stake holders.

IV. CONCLUSION

The present article after reviewing few articles regarding the impact of initiative oriented behaviour of the transformational leaders, on the employees in the organisation. The analysis reveal that there is a need to understand in-depth variables in order to understand specific dimension of the transformational leadership quality which will motivate the employees to smartly in the organisation without fatigue, stress or burnout.

This brings the importance of conducting research with clear and strong research design, which can easily investigate the dimension of specifically to test more complicated relationship.

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